

HUMAN RIGHTS-PRIME FACTOR

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This year, in 2023, the 75th anniversary of the adoption of the Universal Declaration of human rights, which has strengthened the basic democratic principles and requirements in the field of ensuring human rights and freedoms, served as a political, legal basis in the formation of the entire system of international law on this area.

According to the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, a person, his life, honor, dignity, rights and freedoms are of high value. The recognition and protection of human rights and freedoms is the main obligation of the state. This principle occupies a central place in the system of constituent building foundations. Its main feature is the high value of the formation of all other social relations of human rights and freedoms, including state construction.

The priority of human rights as a principle of democratic statehood is included in the foundations of the constitutional order of the Republic of Uzbekistan and is continuous with other principles arising from it, namely the division of power, ideological and political prejudices, multi-party, social justice, self-government of citizens.

It is not for nothing that this year was declared by our president as the "year of attention and quality education for a person" and important and reasonable proposals were put forward.

In recent years, on the initiative of the head of the country, among many subjects, the fact that the course of study "human rights" is taught in all educational institutions serves young people to have sufficient knowledge and skills about their rights and obligations. After all, if the population is sufficiently legally literate and legally civilized, the rights of people will be violated as well as received violations by others.

Indeed, the contribution of the head of state in the reforms carried out in the field of human rights and freedoms in our country is significant.

The presidential decision of PQ-46 "on approval of the National Education Program in the field of human rights in the Republic of Uzbekistan", adopted on February 7, 2023, was an important step towards the implementation of the tasks that our country has taken in this regard. This shows that the head of the state "remains firmly committed to the international obligations of Uzbekistan in the field of human rights".

2021 President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, in his speeches on behalf of the state of Uzbekistan, who participated as a member of the UN Human Rights Council, said that "ensuring basic rights and freedoms of mankind is most important in reforms in Uzbekistan, Sustainable Development Goals are implemented on the principle of "not ignoring anyone", which provides for ensuring the rights and legitimate interests of every person in

The glorification, veneration of a person, the practical provision of his rights and freedoms – is the most important and pressing issue. Therefore, in our country, great work is being carried out in the field of ensuring human rights. Somehow, the life-saving idea of "human interests

above all" is embodied in the framework of reforms in Uzbekistan, which is a clear proof of our opinion that Uzbekistan today cooperates with many countries of the world and large international organizations in various fields. In particular, our state's cooperation with the UN is becoming stronger and more active day by day. We all witnessed that President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, in his speech at the 46th session of the UN Human Rights Council in Geneva, put forward sharp and pressing initiatives aimed at ensuring human interests. This historical speech was met with great satisfaction by the general public, international experts, "there will be no exaggeration to say.

In his speech, the head of state said that the provision of basic human rights and freedoms is the most important in the reforms carried out in Uzbekistan, stating that the goals of Sustainable Development, which were established before 2030, are implemented on the principle of "ignoring no one", which implies the provision of the rights and legitimate interests of each person in our country. We all know very well that these are not simple and loud statements, but, indeed, glorification of a person, expression of his rights and interests, as well as comprehensive maturation have become the main idea of our Constitution. The reason is that all countries that honor human rights, dignity and respect are moving towards progress today.

In this speech of our president, the priorities of further deepening democratic change in Uzbekistan and its activities within the framework of the council are covered by the following seven issues:

first of all, the provision of basic human rights and freedoms is most important in reforms in Uzbekistan;

secondly, to strictly continue work on issues of gender policy aimed at radically increasing the role of women in the socio-political life of the country and in the field of business;

thirdly, it should be noted such as a serious focus on ensuring the rights of persons with special needs.

Separately on all of the above issues, our president stressed that our main achievements are that human rights and legitimate interests are guaranteed in the depths of all our reforms. Also, the passage of the law on children's Ombudsman in 2021, that is, in the International Year for the elimination of child labor, is a vivid evidence of our opinion that the fact is a historical event.

Indeed, in the 21st century, humanity has made great strides in ensuring human rights and freedoms. This can be observed when the importance, position and priority in the formation of national law systems of legal documents adopted on the part of the UN has increased as it has become a prestigious international organization. It is these international legal acts, conventions and treaties that are the main obstacle and protection to the transformation of inhuman, undemocratic phenomena into global reality, we cannot be mistaken.

In this speech, the head of state informed the ratification of the Optional Protocol of the Convention Against Torture, and also touched on the preparation for the invitation of a special speaker on the issue of torture to Uzbekistan in order to work in cooperation on these issues.

A person who considers himself a person, who has a little love in his heart for his homeland, for people, does not hurt anyone, no matter who he is, for the honor, dignity and reputation of other people. It is inherent only in people who are not the virtue of humanity, regardless of their nationality, religion, to oppress, oppress, oppress and endanger someone, to hurt their heart, to wrongfully blame someone, to cause cold relations to fall between two people, to

avoid help and support in harsh conditions, to refuse and cheat, to commit fraud and theft, in a word, to oppress people. After all, the "Koran Karim" strongly condemns these vices, stating in verse 135 of the Surah "An'am": "surely those who are unjust will not be saved", testifying that man is the greatest and most noble being.

In conclusion, it can be said that the views of the president on improving the activities of law enforcement agencies in order to avoid humiliating situations of honor and dignity of people and citizens, adaptation of National connectedness to international standards added by Uzbekistan in the field of human rights, regular monitoring in the field of human rights, strengthening cooperation with international organizations are significant. After all, it is always in our focus to increase the legal culture of the population through activities aimed at strict adherence and respect for the protection of human rights.

